

The importance motivation on teaching and learning English as First and second language

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Abstract: Teachers encourage college students who're inclined or prompted to do their high-satisfactory and achieve their mastering sports. Students' motivation makes coaching and mastering easier, extra thrilling, and extra productive. The contemporary examination confirmed that there are additional behaviors that encourage college students' attitudes toward English Learning after they labored with their friends internal or outdoor the study room. Students' motivation makes coaching and mastering easier, extra thrilling, and extra productive .

Current studies suggest that there are behaviors that stimulate college students' attitudes in the direction of mastering English whilst running with and out of classmates. Given the duty to skip on expertise and abilities to college students, instructors' motivation has ended up an essential factor. And those motives have stimulated the paintings of instructors and college students. Given the duty to skip on expertise and abilities to college students, instructors' motivation has ended up an essential factor. Motivation stimulated the overall performance of the instructor and college students.

Keywords: motivation, characteristics, demotivation, attitudes, and factors that affect learning, teacher`s teaching method, and language skills, types of motivation, varying activities, the effect of class peers in learning, clear information, conclusion.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are many different definitions for the term 'motivation'. Crookes and Schmidt (1991) define motivation as the orientation of the student towards the objectives of learning a second language. According to Broussard and Garrison (2004), motivation is defined as the trait that motivates us to do or not do something. Motivation is defined as "a kind of internal impulse that causes you to do something to achieve something" (Harmer, 2001: 51). As Brown (1994: 152) points out. Without enough motivation even, learners cannot achieve long-term goals. High motivated learner expands effort, takes responsibility, has goals, and desires, and enjoys the process and learning.

High Motivated learners increase their efforts, accept responsibilities, have goals, have desires, and enjoy the process and learning. Due to Steers and Porter (1991: 6), behavior, goals and some forms of feedback are the characteristics of motivation: According to Hawley (1985: 58), to improve the teacher's career

You need to plan your ladder. Some important principles should be developed for a career ladder plan which are:

High performance, financial rewards

- Teachers continue to perform well to maintain higher salaries and status levels.
- There should be no competing rewards that discourage peer interactions and social cognition that are important for effective education.

- You need to use fair and predictable benchmarks. Various studies have shown that motivation is very closely associated with successful language learning.

According to "Steers and Porter (1991:6), motivation can be characterized as follows:

Needs or expectations,

- behavior,
- goals, and
- some form of feedback.

According to Hawley (1985:58), to increase teacher competence, career ladder plans should be done.

There are some principles to be designed for career ladder plans. These are:

For high performance, economic rewards are important.

- To keep higher levels of pay and status, teachers carry on showing high performance.
- There should not be any competitive rewards that can discourage peer interaction and social approval, important to effective teaching.
- Fair and predictable assessment measures should be used.

Various studies have found motivation is very strongly related to achievement in language learning. The teacher then to be asked: Next, you need to ask the teacher a question. What are the reasons and consequences (from motivation and success)? Another question is whether motivation is more or less important than natural learning ability.

As well, motivation enhances cognitive processing domains. Motivation is a basic element in learning English, it is the road to teachers` and students `achievements and teachers` teachings success in (L1) or even (L2) language

Why teachers and trainers should insist on teaching students basic English, especially four skills in that language, With four grammars in a social context.? Situational grammar is highly relevant to learners' participation in the class and has the most direct impact on outcomes such as learning and performance, so it is necessary to teach in the context of both written and spoken English. I have. As teachers, we have found that our classroom needs sufficient motivation to achieve sustainable English learning. Because some of our students are embarrassed to speak English because it requires a lot of enthusiasm. You are not good at English. They find it difficult to speak English in the classroom. Teachers should encourage learners to include particularly shy students in-class and participate in pairs or groups .

The research findings revealed that the performance of teachers was good despite the impact of motivation on learners and vital in accomplishing the goal of education. achievements.

Thus, motivation is critical in improving students' English learning performance. Dornier (1998) emphasized the importance of motivation, which is regarded as a key to learning a second language (L2) and one of the most important factors influencing language learners' success. It is defined as a state that energizes, directs, and sustains actions. Motivation entails goals and necessitates action. It is critical in improving students' English learning performance.

Motivation has a direct impact on how an individual learns and is critical in improving students' English learning performance, whereas demotivation hurts students' performance or achievements.

We noted that students who were fired showed less commitment to classroom activity. In contrast, student engagement shows that motivation extends to the next level when they need to learn and progress in their education.

We must differentiate between motivated and unmotivated students. Throughout the lesson, we encounter demotivated students who exhibit the negative side of motivation, whereas motivated students exhibit the positive side and are more easily described than the demotivated ones.

2. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MOTIVATED LEARNERS

The prompted college students are the maximum a hit rookie, however, they may be now no longer the ones to whom a language comes very effortlessly. Motivated college students are the ones who've positive usual traits as follows:

1 .Positive project orientation:

The learner is inclined to address responsibilities and challenges, his self-assurance in his fulfillment.

2 .Perseverance:

The learner invests an excessive degree of attempt in mastering and isn't discouraged via way of means of setbacks or loss of development.

3 .Ego-involvement:

The learner reveals it is essential to reach mastering to hold his very own high-quality self-image.

4 .Need for fulfillment:

The learner has a wants to reap to triumph over problems and achieve what he units out to do.

5 .High aspirations:

The learner is ambitious and is going for challenges and pinnacle grades.

6 .Goal orientation:

The learner may be very privy to the dreams of mastering and directs his efforts toward attaining them.

7 .Tolerance of ambiguity:

The learner isn't either annoyed or demotivated via way of means scenario regarding lack of expertise or circumfusion can stay with those patiently, withinside the self-assurance that expertise will come later.

3. DIFFERENT DISTINCTIONS OF MOTIVATION

There are four main types of motivation: instrumental, integrative, intrinsic, and extrinsic motivation.

1 .In the literature a difference is made between the "incorporated and instrumental dynamistic. Integrated dynamics describes rookies who need to combine into the way of life of the second language organization and take part in social sports withinside the organization. Gardner and Lambert have delivered those principles and asserted that integrative motivation has an extra effect on rookies of various languages, however, studies have refuted the software of this statement to people who analyze distinctive languages. language rookies in fashionable, however, any other examination shows that came to be not possible to differentiate am between two.

2 .Another difference between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic approach the arouse college students participated in mastering hobby for their own sake. Extrinsic approach motivation is derived from critical incentives. It is derived from the effect of a few outside incentives.

Many assets of extrinsic motivation are in handy to affect the instructor. The extra assured college students end up, the extra capacity to understand such fulfillment on their very own, the much less they may want express guidance from a person else.

3 .A 1/3 difference has been made between "global", "situational" and project "motivation"

Dornyei (1998) positioned pressure as the effect of motivation, which is taken into consideration as a key to mastering a 2d or overseas language. (L2) and one of the largest elements affecting language rookies` fulfillment. The contemporary examination effect confirmed that there have been techniques and behaviors that encourage college students to inspire college students to analyze English Learners may be extra prompted whilst their parents supported and recommended them to analyze English. Students must recognize the cause of mastering English is, to enhance the rookies` 4 abilities and to master; listening, speaking, reading, and writing abilities to Al-Hosni (2014, p. 23.1996) says that speaking is the maximum talent for many of the 4 abilities; (listening, speaking, reading, and writing).

Macintyre (1999) believed secure weather is essential for motivation and rookies experience cushy to analyze a language on this condition.

Good and Brophy (1994) said that motivation can not be advanced in a hard study room and instructors must create powerful mastering surroundings for her their kids. They endured that powerful language mastering takes place in comfortable and pleasant elegance. However, oral language, while utilized by the instructor, rarely features as an approach for college kids to benefit expertise and discover thoughts." Thus, whilst we educate, we must consciousness of

the 4 abilities: listening, speaking, reading, and writing to broaden the 4 abilities of our college students to beautify college students' motivation, they may be prompted. Many questions may be requested approximately the effect of motivation on the English rookies:

What distinctive forms of techniques appear to be the maximum motivating for the scholars to analyze the goal language? Are rookies high-quality or bad toward language mastering; the 4 abilities, with the vocabulary abilities and grammar situationally?

Does their motivation come inside them (intrinsic) or comes from detail outdoor of themselves (extrinsic)? Why is mastering vocabulary so essential? To solve, the questions Because of the sturdy effect of vocabulary mastering techniques must guide motivation this is immediately affecting the 4 English abilities. It fostered integrative motivation. And it complements the rookies' motivation to analyze the goal language and explicit themselves in those 4 abilities.

In Situational Motivation, instructors can do much stuff to create a study room surroundings that motivate college students to analyze and behave in approaches that sell their lengthy-time period fulfillment .

Evans and John (1998, p. 199) country, "in communicate exercise, it's miles higher than the scholars are divided into pair and organization for the huge size, after which making a few questions and responding is received from different organizations". They additionally imply, "Based on a few experts, oral communicate exercise can be higher if the interplay is worried in pair and organization paintings. So, the scholars can be loose to explicit their very own thoughts and construct the sentences. That is, oral interplay includes flip-making and questing strategy .

Teachers should recognize that there are elements that preclude rookies from being prompted, and the goal of coaching unique techniques plays an important function. They must take them into their consideration, some elements lead college students to be prompted; whilst others cause them to be demotivated. Through my lengthy revel in, player college students have extra prompted in any elegant hobby whilst instructors supply them clean facts why they may be worried approximately its intention.

Students' motivation can be stepped forward for the subsequent motives: the instructor cares for encouraging their fulfillment with appraisal words, if the instructor behaves toward his college students in a pleasant way withinside the study room, by no means forestall or interrupt them for committing at each unmarried mistake or errors .

Mistakes should be corrected later gently. Teachers must set up a proper rapport together with their college students. Students are now no longer to be punished for the sake of elegance-subject. Empirical research display college students who're puzzled if their extraordinary classmates mock their mispronunciation of positive words .

When college students are fascinated and keen to analyze they may be extra prompted. Class chaos and crowded demotivate player college students. On the opposite proper elegance manipulation and control are elements that encourage college students to analyze .

Consequently, the function of motivation is so essential, that talking English is a part of the instructor's function. Since our college students want an education that is primarily based totally on motivation. Motivation is a have to in coaching English as (L2) language. Successful instructor constantly is privy to supplying their college students with ok motivation to analyze the language. Several influential elements affect a learner's motivation: inner elements and different outside elements encompass factors associated with mastering context, and power that encourage a learner to pursue a path of action. Teachers of English can encourage their college students via way of means of following their achievements and giving them the essential zeal to perform their research. A good instance of, this is the ongoing evaluation of oral and written abilities as it's miles called listening, speaking, reading, and writing .

It is understood that motivation begins off evolved at the start degrees of the kid's existence, at domestic. A baby is prompted via way of means of his parents to apply the parent's tongue to explicit his thought, thoughts, and feeling. If the kid is prompted via way of means of his instructor to analyze English as (L2) with the assistance of his (L1). He can effortlessly analyze English .

What is motivation? Are our college students prompted extrinsically or intrinsically to analyze? Do they analyze the language to keep away from punishment or benefit from praise? What are motivation and its impact on mastering the language?

4. WHY IS MOTIVATION IMPORTANT IN THE TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESS?

Motivation is one of the maximum essential principles in psychology. The perception is likewise of fantastic significance in language education. Our college students want a variety of motivations, intrinsic and extrinsic motivations in mastering .

Intrinsic motivation for arousing their hobbies to analyze the goal language with a bit of luck. To educate college students in English intrinsically they must take delivery of a puzzle workout to clear up the trouble to discover it as a difficult opposition.

In contrast, extrinsic motivation is whilst our college students do something to achieve praise or keep away from punishment. In this case, it's miles understood the motivation for the pupil is conduct that comes from something outdoor of himself, together with an award or proper grade.

How can instructors boom their college students wants to analyze the language?

What are the sports which could instructors arouse their college students` hobbies?

Are instructors privy to coaching the concern count expertise and hyperlink it to a feel of ways rookies analyze their actual existence?

What are the varieties of motivation?

5. TYPES OF MOTIVATION

Intrinsic motivation is, for arousing the scholars` hobbies to analyze the goal language with a bit of luck. Teachers may also educate college students English language intrinsically. By asking them to clear up a puzzle workout or write a letter opposition. Students are worried to clear up the trouble or write a proper letter as, of difficult opposition.

In contrast, extrinsic motivation is whilst our college students do something to achieve praise or keep away from punishment. In this case, it's miles understood the motivation for the pupil is conduct that comes from something outdoor of himself, together with an award or proper grade.

How can instructors boom their college students` wants to analyze the language?

How can they encourage their college students to analyze English?

What are the coaching methods that instructors ought to make use of to arouse their college students` hobbies to analyze English?

Varying strategies and techniques to beautify college students` motivation: Although each instructor wishes to have a variety of effective and powerful conduct control strategies and be sponsored up via way of means of the institute device that permit all of us in which they stand, save you many subject issues arising. Poor coaching techniques have an awful effect on the scholars` achievements. Through various coaching techniques, instructors encourage their college students and offer them the possibility to experience domestic. Besides, those coaching techniques permit college students to use what they learned withinside the study room for actual-existence experiences .

Varying coaching techniques, instructors have verified to be a powerful manner of each disseminating and integrating expertise; they cause cooperative mastering and life coaching. Part of the instructors` jobs, is motivating college students; encouraging them, arousing their hobbies and dreams, and improving their willingness to analyze.

By giving college students the self-assurance to have interaction in elegance-discussion. The college students` emotional and intellectual cap potential that they cause them to do what they need in a pleasant atmosphere. If rookies handiest do matters due to the fact they may be obeying commands, with no attention to goals, or ambitions of the lesson that outcomes involvement in selections; they may be not likely to broaden their private duty for his or her very own mastering .But the high-satisfactory thing is to create in them the spirit of opposition; the pleasant spirit, the spirit of willingness to co-perform and use the language and to assist every different in pair-paintings or organization-paintings .

Empirical research implies that relatively prompted college students analyze quicker and higher than the shy and disinterested ones, whilst demotivated or low achievers may also face a lot of problems speaking with their pees than the extraordinary ones. Although, several instructors trust that rookies aren't prompted to talk English until they enhance their communicative capacities .Having the incentive and possibilities college students can use the language freely and companion the language authentically in actual existence, college students are capable of making their interplay going on.

Teachers who're proper at what they do. They should take advantage of coaching technological media: visible and audio-approach in undertaking their lesson to attract their college students` hobbies to analyze .

Conditions of motivation: What are the situations that boom motivation? According to Gardner and Lambert (1972), rookies are prompted to analyze after they consider themselves as a ready person, cope with substances organized to their degree, see the intention of their sports, see their research as significant, are given hard paintings, stay in secure surroundings have the danger to explicit mental wishes for fulfillment, recognition, and acceptance, suppose that the mastering is for them and now no longer for his or her instructors, paintings with thrilling substances, to make selections and experience duty for participating, and revel in extra fulfillment than failure.

6. THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING GRAMMAR AND VOCABULARY AS ORAL OR WRITTEN SKILLS:

Moreover, instructors are thinking about coaching grammar and vocabulary objects are the street to constructing sentences that might assist college students to vanish out their problems in mastering spoken and written abilities. Teachers must be privy to learners' fulfillment or failures; their motivation or demotivation to analyze the goal language have to be monitored in elegance interplay. Other cookies are not anything to be embarrassed about proper rookies who understand this, take setbacks in their stride, and search for approaches to take advantage of them to be triumphant subsequent time. Who are the demotivated college students and prompted ones? What are their traits?

Dornyei (1998) defined demotivation as unique outside forces that lessen or lessen the motivational foundation of behavioral purpose or ongoing action. Demotivated rookies display a loss of hobby withinside the (L2) elegance sports .

Negative- pupil may also experience now and then they don't have any intimate elegance- mates; due to the fact they experience remoted from their different friends in any elegance sports. They will count on failure if they may be overlooked .

Dornyei (1998) defined demotivation as unique outside forces that lessen or lessen the motivational foundation of a behavioral purpose or ongoing action. Demotivated rookies display a loss of hobby withinside the L2 or L2 network way of life, hesitate to take part in any elegant sports, and don't have any intimate association with the instructor or friends.

7. THE CHARACTERISTICS OF DEMOTIVATED STUDENTS:

The result of the examination among instructors and college students recommends there are a few elements that affect college students` willingness. All the subsequent elements make mastering the procedure hard (Jafari,2013): As I stated in my studies, there are numerous motives for college kids` demotivation; the dearth of motivation itself, and that has an awful effect negatively on each instructor's rookies` components together with the subsequent: Demotivated college students display:

1. Disinterestedness
2. A susceptible choice
3. Laziness
4. Shyness
5. Lack of motion of one`s abilities
6. Lack of vanity or diffidence
7. Lack of self-assurance
8. Lack of expertise, now no longer analyzing sufficient
9. Having bodily or intellectual issues

There are numerous approaches instructors can undertake to arouse hobbies in their projects. Every instructor wishes pedagogical motivation to educate rookies on the goal language. They should their techniques of arousing hobbies amongst rookies.

And this refers to the cap potential to arouse withinside the college students a choice to analyze the language and feeling that the language they may be mastering is beneficial for or their profession.

They must recognize powerful coaching techniques to apprehend the dreams or goals of the lesson surely and underlie overseas language mastering. Teachers must encourage college students toward the subject of the day simply at the whole degrees of the lesson. Moreover, instructors must range the sports, responsibilities substances to do away with boredom in study room routines, to keep away from demotivation. Some college students at distinctive tiers, at our institute, their hobbies aren't sturdy, mainly they want motivation and exuberance to analyze the language freely.

Learners must be privy to the goals of the project each language mastering and content. Highly prompted college students do now no longer want a great deal of motivation however poorly- prompted college students to want numerous reasons to arouse their hobbies to analyze the language.

As a count of fact, motivation is, converted into developing the choice amongst college students to analyze English as an overseas or 2d language in an amusing manner as enjoyment produces satisfaction which in its flip motivates the mastering procedure. If the instructor does now no longer offer incentives to set off rookies to analyze the language, their fulfillment will necessarily be meager. As, I started the whole thing relies upon the instructor; the substances, which include the audio-visible aids, the exceptional coaching and study room, suitable texts and aids, communicative sports, and the mastering setting. The hitting instructor, himself represents sturdy motivational elements.

Such incentives shape the using pressure that makes, coaching extra powerful as proper traits coaching, suitable texts and aids, communicative sports, and the mastering setting. It is thought that motivation is the mental procedure this refers to fashionable conduct. Thus, motivation is the procedure itself and the reason is the concrete purpose for sporting out the action. There are distinctive varieties of reasons; the number one reasons, and the secondary reasons are critical to apprehending motivation.

Intrinsic motivation: wherein originates internally of the character. It represents all the matters that encourage college students primarily based totally on inner rewards.

The Extrinsic Motivation: whilst this kind of motivation originates or arises from outdoor character; it refers to conduct this is pushed via way of means of outside rewards together with: money, fame, grades, and praise.

The number one motivation; wherein hobby comes from domestic and the instructor is a super scenario now no longer regularly met whilst, in different words, it's miles the coaching procedure that has the best effect on the learner's motivation. Such as beneath neath the manipulation of the instructor who videoes displays units of the mastering procedure to maintain the scholars' hobby in mastering the language, together with the scholars' competence of mastering the language, his fulfillment, his creativity, his incentive mastering, and physiological mastering.

The secondary motivation: wherein hobby from outdoor the learner is extra essential because it passed off in our institute college students.

When the fascinated instructor should supply the rookie's brilliant facts approximately the ambitions in their mastering and relate the ambitions to his college students' wishes. He has to explain to them how the expertise of the overseas language can be beneficial for them their future.

A ready skilled - instructor, varies his coaching strategies and provides quite a few study room sports that play a critical element in motivating college students and facilitating the purchase of an overseas language. As a count of fact, research display that player college students have been prompted whilst instructors supply clean facts why they may be worried about a hobby and approximately its intention.

We discover instructors can lessen the monotony of the stress of ritual withinside the study room and make mastering extra pupil-focused and much less teacher-focused. In organization paintings or pair paintings, instructors should range their coaching techniques.

Teachers must be additionally privy to numerous sports which could encourage college students which are distinctive a few encompass: function-gambling, trouble solving; others mock interviews, study room debates, contests in writing stories, letter-opposition, and mastering and imparting playlets.

If college students are requested to be participated in gambling video games, appearing function-gambling, play-acting, open-ended cues, video games, and sports. Such sports have a fantastic effect, completed in organizations wherein college students trade character applicable facts collectively and can assist them to arouse their dreams, and hobbies to analyze the language in an exciting atmosphere. Therefore, Varied sports are of fantastic significance. Such numerous sports switch the procedure of mastering from 'talent-getting' to 'talent-the use of '. The mastering scenario may be stimulating to the scholars.

The fascinated, prompted instructors must encourage their college students toward the subject of the day simply at the whole degrees of the lesson. And inspire them to analyze new facts with their college students' friends withinside the mastering procedure. Teachers must be privy to participating college students' demotivation. And college students must be additionally privy to their mastering surroundings.

Teachers direct them to take part, mainly people who and shortage of coaching abilities. display to be shy Schools do now no longer manipulate all the elements that affect college students' educational engagement. . Teachers' skillful instruction, and the guide college students' wishes

To pursue their instructional and professional dreams. I trust college students whose parents are knowledgeable are proper reasons to inspire their youngsters to reap excessive tiers of overall performance withinside the overseas language and vice versa; the uneducated parents. So, parents have a fantastic effect on their youngsters to pursue better research in the future. They encourage them to journey overseas to retain their better education.

We as, instructors or running shoes should insist on coaching rookies on the essentials of the language mainly the 4 abilities of the language: listening, Speake, and reading. English Grammar must study social context. Situational Grammar must study with the 4 abilities in each written and oral English language ability for its fantastic significance.

8. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, teachers should give learners adequate opportunities, to be enhanced to practice their speaking through motivation and to be involved in the class activities. Motivation plays a vital role in the learning process without motivation students cannot achieve their goals. Teachers could not achieve their task to teach if they neglected or failed to arouse the students' motivation to learn. Internal or external motives are the most important factors that can affect the teachers' and learners' performance. Trainers or teachers cannot depend completely on the students' interests and desires for learning the target language. External motives are adequate remunerative factors for the absence of the spontaneous desire to learn the target language. Motivation is a key role in developing language activities. It is Motivation and Enthusiasm manifest as desire and interest, and as a driving force that pushes teachers and learners to act and pursue their goals.

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